

The influence of political advertisements on voter's intention: a case study of main stream political parties of Pakistan

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this study is to look into how voters' intentions are affected by political advertisements from Pakistan's major political parties, such as the Pakistan Peoples Party PPP, Pakistan Muslim League Nawaz, PML-N, and Pakistan TehreekInsaf, PTI. This study used a quantitative methodology, and 1,000 people were surveyed. Data was collected from five main divisions of Pakistan. The study's findings demonstrated that favorable attitudes towards PPP, PML-N, and PTI commercials positively impacted attitudes towards these political parties. The findings showed that favorable perceptions of the PPP, PML-N, It was also discovered that voters' intentions were influenced to support PML-N and PTI by positive attitudes towards their commercials, but not the PPP by positive attitudes towards its advertisements. Positive cognition regarding the PML-N and PTI advertising was found to influence voters' intentions in favor of these parties, whereas positive cognition regarding the PPP advertisements did not influence voters' intentions in favor of the PPP. The findings additionally indicated that voters' intentions were surveyed in favor of PML-N and PTI by favorable perceptions of these parties, but not in favor of PPP from positive perceptions. The results of this study show that political commercials are effective instruments for forming opinions and have a big influence on voters' intentions.

Keywords: Social Media, Influence, Political, Advertising, Voter, Intention.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

Media has an integral role in shaping rather building public opinion (Tang, 2005) or perception about any imperative aspect of social, economic, political, national or international issue (Esser, 2013). The role of media cannot be negated in today's modern era. Owing to its importance in governance, each state either being headed by any military or civilian dictator, king, monarch or even democratic government uses media as a powerful tool of controlling public opinion (Cheibub et al., 2010; Geddes et al., 2014), building public perception in favor of the government (Anderson & Stansfield, 2005). In order to achieve its motives, different states put social, economic and political pressure through various state's institutions to control the 'veins' of the media (Centeno, 2002; George, 2012).

Although, media has a very controlled role where dictatorial states are in power or monarchs or kings are ruling the countries (Suwannathat-Pian, 2013). However, its role is quite different in democratic states (Christians et al., 2010). In fact, the media in the democratically functioning countries is considered to be an important factor in determining and strengthening the accountability and sustainability of the Government (Lenssen et al., 2006). Different political parties utilize the component of media for their vested interests including influencing public opinion in favor of the leaders of the political parties (Gamson, 2004). Accordingly, the media plays an important role and the forums offered on the election day became an important platform for political parties to put forward their political ideology (Brown, 2013); Graham & Hajru, 2011). The political parties across the world especially in democratic countries project their political manifestos and 'inject' media message in their minds while using media as a powerful effects paradigm (Gibson, 2009; Onis, 1997) and thousands of voters or followers of the political leaders are highly influenced by the media campaigns launched by various political leaders and the parties they are heading (Parmelee & Bichard, 2011; Vaccari & Valeriani, 2015).

The vitality of media is increased manifold during election seasons when political leaders do not speak or address their rallies and processions in absence of media or mikes of multiple television channels (Blake, 2016). Different political leaders believe public is highly influenced by the media campaigns therefore they have made media as a mandatory tool to spread their messages effectively to mass population (Katz & Lazarsfeld, 1966; Shirky, 2011). In fact, media also provide electors with the opportunity to receive political information and analyze the programs (Dalton et al., 1998) and lists that political parties and candidates have raised and disseminated during the election campaign (Farrell et al., 2001). So, election campaigns are quite incomplete without media (Esser, 2013). In fact, at several occasions, media guide political leaders and their party leaders to adopt some strategies to make their statements and even their campaigns effective (Jacobs & Shapiro, 2000). Thus effectiveness of messages and political statements are highly dependent on the role of media during elections (Davis, 2007; Mazzoleni & Schulz, 1999).

1.2 Significance of Media

All formats of media have great significance with certain variance of effectiveness of media messages (Grigorovici & Constantin, 2004). However, one cannot deny the importance of media in making political campaigns successful (Benoit, 2007). Generally, a large number of population in Pakistan believe social media especially Twitter played a vital role in projecting political manifesto of the ruling party of Pakistan Tehrik-e-Insaf led by Premier Imran Khan. According to political leaders and newsmen, it was mass media in general and social media specifically which highlighted rather enhanced political stature of the PTI Chairman Imran Khan (Muslim et al., 2014).

It was the media which provided opportunity of boom and boasted the political strength of the PTI thus paving the ways of power corridors (Gayer, 2014). Due to effective

social media policies, PTI entered the Parliament while other political parties including former ruling party Pakistan Muslim League Nawaz and Pakistan People Party remained unsuccessful due to lack of having a hand on the right vein of the social media (Khan & Naqvi, 2018). Therefore, PTI utilized the significance of social media in right way and highly influenced the supporters and followers of the political party (Bilal et al., 2019; Rao, 2020). Due to effective media campaign and preemptive media strategy, Imran Khan was able to form the political government (Khan et al., 2020). Now, media channels are in the firm fist (Lent, 1989) and the PTI led government is controlling the institution of media through different public departments including Pakistan Electronic Media Regulatory Authority (PEMRA).

Accordingly, different applications of mass media including television, radio, FM radio channels, newspapers, magazines, brochures, internet and other formats of mass media are considered the powerful tool of maneuvering public opinion and voter's intention towards voting process (Dominick, 2010). For example, television was once believed to be the most powerful tool of motivating public opinion for favorable political parties, dictatorial regimes, dictators and kings in their favor (Tang, 2005). Before television, newspaper was believed to be sole source of providing information and was considered the most authentic source of information. According to findings of different studies, the public trusted in the news and information carried by the newspapers, broadcasted by the radios and telecasted by the televisions to the great extent (Washbourne, 2010).

According to findings of a study, the public became aware with the word 'propaganda' in later part of such inventions and accordingly they were educated about the misuse, maneuvering or agenda setting purposes of the newspapers, radios and television (Alina, 2020). The World War I provided public about various techniques of propaganda that radio was being used as a propaganda war technique by the powerful forces of the World War I (Horten, 2003). In any case, the importance of different applications of the mass media cannot be negated because regardless it was used as a propaganda weapon even then it had great significance because of the public trust in such applications (MacDonald, 2003).

1.3 Media in Dictatorial Regime

As discussed above, media play different roles in different forms of government including the military led state or in kingdom headed by a monarch or the king or the dictator in any form (Finer, 2002). There are two broader categories of the role of media including. First, role of media in dictatorial regime, and secondly, role of media in a democratic country (Rozumilowicz, 2002). In both forms of governance, the effectiveness of media remains highly effective (Van-Dijck, 2013). In first form of governance, i.e., dictatorship, the media becomes a tool of projecting the stature of military leadership, promotes developmental projects led by the military ruling class (Cook, 2007; Harb, 2003) and even build image of the military dictators through various tools of image building including public relations, advertising, etc. (Kunczik, 2003). However, critics believed the advertising during the military rule is always ambiguous in the eyes of the general public because most of the civilians believed the military rule is a hegemonic rule (Gershovich, 2000) where there is no political freedom and political participation of the elected members of the parliaments (Kapiszewski, 2006; Kassa, 2015).

But even then, media has an effective role in popularizing the catchy slogans of the military rulers through paid content i.e., advertisements (Frith & Mueller, 2010; Sharma & Singh, 2006; Zhao, 1998). During a 'political presidential election' to elect General Ayyub Khan, the military regime prepared and launched advertisement campaigns in such a way that all other civilian contestants for presidency including Mohtaram Fatima Jinnah, sister of the Father of the Nation, Quaid-e-Azam Muhammad Ali Jinnah, Wali Khan, Sheikh Mujib-ur-Rehman and others were labelled as traitors of the State (Sohail, 2015).

The advertisements were projecting rather building image of the military dictator while crushing rather polluting the political stature of the opponents in the eyes of the public (Derby, 2009; Rutherford, 2000). Accordingly, during another military regime of General Zia, media was the virtual mouthpiece of the military government (Hassan, 2018). According to critics, media could not flourish or function independently during the military era led by Gen. Zia (Burki, 1988; Shah, 2012). One could not even speak or write a single word against then President General Zia-ul-Haq (Ziring, 1988) and his 'achievements' rather media had to function in accordance with the directions of Zia.

1.4 Significance of the Study

Voter's intention always plays a vital role in voting to specific candidate or the political party. Such intention is developed from various socioeconomic factors, political sloganeering, projection on media etc. Political advertisement is believed to be the major factor affecting the voter's intention to vote or change his/ her decision to vote to specific party contrary to his/ her predetermined decision. Different formats of mass media including television channels, radio, newspapers, magazines and social media are also considered effective channels of transmitting messages of government functionaries, ministers, politicians, bureaucrats and others. This study has been designed to develop comprehension about effects of political advertisements on voter's intention.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Media Campaigning for Political Activation

Vohs et al., (2014) believed 'choice' is a characteristic that directly leads to a decision making power an individual enjoys with consciousness (Bakewell & Mitchell, 2003). We cannot perform our routine tasks in our daily life if we lack a decision making power (Deetz, 1992) therefore it can be affirmed that confidence, choice, decision making power and the strength to decide matters and perform actions are the abilities of a person to spend a peaceful life (Gregory et al., 2012; Tulsy, 2005).

2.2 Voters' Choice

Sundström et al., (2017) argued that ranging from routine tasks to economic development, societal progress, cultural achievements, political empowerment and national growth (Delle Fave, Massimini, & Bassi, 2011), there are prominent individuals including politicians, intellectuals, academicians, journalists, bureaucrats, social activists and other people who contribute to individual, collective and national development through their active participation in evolution process (Dawson, 1996; Feagin et al., Dyer (2004) stated that everyone in a society is playing his/ her role in a society in which the individual resides. Since, the study in hand is linked with influence of political advertisements on intentions of the voters to decide for voting their likeminded political party or leader, we observe the decision making power plays an integral role in developing behavior to vote any specific person or the party (Michels & De Graaf, 2010; Strom, 1990). According to Knoke (1994), the choice of the individual or the group is dependent on several socio-economic and political factors including their intentions, social pressure, normative approach and political, ethnic and cultural affiliation as well.

According to a study conducted by Verplanken and Holland (2002), choice and decision making power play a significant role in developing behavior to vote. Tyburek et al., (2010) stated that voting behavior is the most complex behavior in our social life as explained by the political scientists through the lens of political psychology. Chapp (2012) believed that politically motivated behavior of the voters is always charged with the affective behavior which is directly imparted among the voters through social pressure, political actors, political scientists, sophistication and political attentiveness. Political

electrical psychology contains the methods and ways including feelings, emotions, memory, and other socio-economic and political factors which affect individuals' behavior thus empowering them to vote for a specific political party or the leaders (Masters & Sullivan, 1990; Ratner, 2002). Htun (2004) and Legee et al., (2009) argued that gender, race, ethnicity, religion and culture etc., collectively constitute a voting behavior, so, these are the psychological factors which play a due role in decision making power of the citizens to vote to their likeminded political leaders. Kenned (2008) and Boltanski (1999) stated that media pressure is always built to target the undecided voters, who do not have deep convictions while this pressure could be built through constant messages of both direct first-level opinions and indirect second level hints. Political leaders take shelters in media assistance for motivating their voters. Schill and Kirk (2017) shared that political candidates make effective attempt on undecided voters to motivate them through different sloganeering of individual, regional as well as national development. Accordingly, such voters are highly influenced by the political advertisements run the television channels (Prat & Strömberg, 2005; Shaw, 1999).

Moreover, the political candidates enhance political pressure through with the guns of media in accordance with the size or the volume of the voters. According to a study conducted by Druckman (2003) and Entman and Rojecki (2001), television news programs develop certain images about any issue or aspect of any issue in the minds of the television viewers. The study says the program, first presented by Lippmann, refers to the way in which we form the images in our minds. Dalton et al. (1998), represents another concept in connection with this question what promises that voters identify with their election of the party because they perceive the goals of the party are compatible with their own part of the electorate. According to Kim (2017) and Bache, Bartle, and Flinders (2016), the voters generally have faith and certain beliefs which assist them to vote for their likeminded political candidate. By doing so, the voters examine their need and political stature of their candidate. According to the analysis of the voters by Smith (2011), the voters make their mind based on their needs of individual as well as societal growth and take promises from the political leaders to fulfill their promises once he/she comes into power. According to a study carried out by Rao (2020), this is the dilemma of not only underdeveloped countries but the first world countries are also involved in launching media campaigns to convince their voters to support their likeminded political leaders or the political parties. This is the result of media outreach to common. Before influx of social as well as traditional and digital media, common person was dependent on single source of information. However, in today's era, even a common man residing in village areas in developed countries have access to information and updates about socio-economic developments in the country (Madon, 2000; Mbaiwa, 2005). Now, political actors have to forcibly utilize all means of communication including paid content to influence their voters and keep them having faith in their favorite political leaders.

2.3 Political Advertisements and South Asian Countries

Media also play a leading role in guiding, convincing and persuading voters for specific party or the political leaders. The eastern democratic countries have utilized different forms of media to persuade their publics to get favorable results. The Asian countries where there is a democratic form of government, media is considered the fourth pillar of the state and in pure democracies, media acts as the first pillar because it is tasked to safeguard the ideological boundaries, psychological attacks of the enemy and the war of information and disinformation in eastern countries including Indonesia and other states. According to Kushner (2007) and Belmonte (2013), the political leaders of Asian and South Asian countries are highly influenced by the way Hitler utilized Radio as a propaganda tool and spread disinformation to defeat his enemies through psychological warfare and the model was highly accepted by Japanese imperial forces. Hitler's model of propaganda as

envisaged by his Propaganda Minister Dr. Joseph was taken as a unique approach of psychological warfare in South Asian countries. According to study, Indian politicians were the most vulnerable political leaders exposed to media strategy to influence their voters. For instance, their voters are confused between the bombardments of different political advisement campaigns launched from different parties to project as well as negative their rival leaders. The study showed that Indian politicians influenced different classes of Indian society with different media strategies. Even, there are different media policies and tactics adopted in different states for different classes and regions. For instance, Indian politicians of upper class used argumentative strategy discussing development, industrial growth and economic development to influence business community, businessperson, industrialists, property tycoons and other influential but business oriented people. According to Yezbick (2009), Indian politician used 'luring slogans' of economic development, job opportunities, status enhancement etc. for the upper middle and middle class through the lens of media. According to the findings, the slogans like property alleviation, eradication of corruption, providing fundamental rights etc., were used in media campaigns to impress and influence the people residing in villages, poor sites for voting their favorable party (Htoo, 2019).

3. Theoretical Framework

Information Integration Theory

Developed and hectically tested by Norman Anderson (1971-1991), Information Integration Theory (IIT) basically discussed that how behaviors and attitudes are formed with the amalgamation of pre-existing and on-going thoughts are combined to form an attitude (Wilmshurst, 2013). The IIT says a persuasive message is coded as information and the information has two specific characteristics including value, and weight. The first concept of 'value' is linked with assessment of the information i.e., whether the piece of the information shall be valuable or invaluable whereas the 'weight' is interlinked with the 'weightage' or 'significance' of the information. For instance, first of all an individual would assess any piece of information is certainly valuable or not and secondly he/she would assess if the piece of information were valuable then to what extent the information is valuable? Therefore, IIT explains that whatever we receive in the shape of information in our routine life, if the information carries certain weightage, then how can such sort of information affect our attitude and press us to behave in specific circumstances. Based on the above-said discussion, it can be argued that the new information received through persuasive messages is integrated, combined and mixed up with the pre-existing information to shape up or even create a new attitude among us. So, this theory stresses upon the mixing up the previous and fresh information shaping up a new attitude. Therefore, it can be said that we read newspapers, watch television, read books, search and examine records and even interact with each other, our discussion or action, or behavior based on the previous information creates a new debate, new idea, new discussion or a new attitude. The above-said theory is highly interlinked with the study in hand. As the researcher intended to examine the influence of political advertisements on the voter's intention in Pakistan, the Information Integration Theory (IIT) seems the most appropriate approach to conduct the study in the said paradigm. The voters have their pre-determined beliefs, liking and disliking about different political parties and political leaders not only in Pakistan but also across the world. Voters are highly influenced by the sloganeering of the political leaders and educated voters are certainly impressed by the manifestos of the parties.

For instance, there are a significant number of Pakistani populations, which is highly influenced by the manifesto of Pakistan People Party, another huge ratio is highly impressed by the manifesto and developmental approach of the Pakistan Muslim League Nawaz. A huge number also likes the incumbent government led by Pakistan Tehrik-e-

Insafwith premiership of Imran Khan. All of the voters have some personal beliefs to vote to their likeminded political party. As discussed in the Information Integration Theory, a large number of voters in Interior Sindh and Southern Punjab vote for PPP due to social pressure of elders, landlords whereas normative approach also plays a key role in constituting strength of the voters to make a decision to vote for a specific leader or his/ her likeminded political party. The voters voting for PPP believe in famous slogan of the party 'Roti, KapraaurMakan' as they believe if the PPP comes into power, it shall provide 'bread, dress and shelter' to the needy ones. The same thing happened with the voters of PTI who voted to the party thus paving the course of bringing it into power. They believed the party would eradicate corruption from the country's public institutions, it shall empower the policy of merit, curb nepotism etc. needless to say the actual outcome of the party after coming into power, the voters intention was quite positive in voting to PTI. They believe they should provide 'a chance' to Imran Khan as he used to fulminate at the past political leaders especially Asif Ali Zardari and Mian Nawaz Sharif while labeling them as 'corrupt' and 'dishonest'. Therefore, the intention of the voters matters a lot. Such intention is highly influenced by the normative approach, social pressure and behavioral intention as well. As well as the theory of information integration is concerned, the study in hand also believes the information provided by the political leaders is decoded from their persuasive messages to impress their voters and they make their perception about the political party. Therefore, the researcher believes the study would approve the Information Integration Theory in political circumstances of Pakistan pertaining to developing voting behavior of the voters of all political parties.

4. Methodology

4.1 Research Design

This study is quantitative in nature and the research paradigm falls under positivism paradigm which advocates the quantitative method. The research design is causal (cause and effect) to measure and examine the causal relationship of political advertisements over voters' intention. Subsequently, the effects of political advertisement on voter's intention are of imperative nature. Language and images play a vital role in developing a powerful links between message and target audiences. For instance, the language adopted in political advertisements and the images of politicians, manifestos etc. not only make advertisement effective but such advertisements enhance understanding of the voters about cultural context. All these components in advertisements have some impact on voter's intention. The Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) allows all the citizens of or above the age of 18 years to vote and they cast their votes. There is no discrimination of ethnicity, gender, caste, color or creed. The study in hand is cross-sectional quantitative study by using a structured questionnaire carrying closed ended questions as an instrument of data collection. The study is unique because the focus of the research is to examine the influence of advertisements of different political parties of Pakistan on the intention of the voters living in different geographical locations.

4.2 Population of the Study

In most of the countries, democratically elected government is chosen by the vote of the citizens who hold Computerized National Identity Cards (CNIC) issued by NADRA which is awarded to them after attaining the age of 18 years. In this study, researcher has also chosen only those respondents who are eligible to cast their vote. Furthermore, it has also been observed that illiterate and uneducated people are highly influenced by political advertisements regarding voting intention as compared to the educated and literate persons (Fujiwara, 2015). There are certain factors behind this bifurcation as well, as the uneducated and illiterate voters have less chances of confirmation of information due to

limited exposure to media (Driscoll & Nelson, 2014). Whereas the educated and literate persons have great access to media and they can easily check the authenticity of the information shared to them through political advertisements (Kellner & Share, 2007).

4.3 Sample

The researcher has collected data from 1,000 individuals who belonged to five districts of Punjab province of Pakistan including Lahore, Faisalabad, Sargodha, Multan, and Bahawalpur. They were asked about their opinion regarding the influence of political advertisements on their voting intention. Purposive sampling technique was adopted to collect data from only those respondents, who were aged above 18 years and exposed to political advertisements. Respondents with different age groups and qualification both literate and illiterate were included in the sample. The sample has been taken because of proportional allocation method as 200 respondents were selected from each selected district of Punjab province regardless of urban or rural areas of their residence.

4.4 Data Collection Tool

In order to examine the influence of political advertisements on voter's intention, the structured questionnaire has been used to collect data. First, five questions about demographics are included: gender, age, profession, years of education, and their social class. Then two questions related to the voting preferences are asked. One is about last general elections held in 2018, and the other is related to the general elections to be held in 2023. As per study carried out on 800 adolescents, consumer's attitude towards ethnic advertisement has also a direct relationship between the message conveyed in ethnic advertisement and the subsequent attitude of the consumers. Then 60 opinion statements related to the effect of political advertisements are included. These statements are divided by four main scales which are adapted: 1) Attitude toward political advertisements; 2) Cognition about political advertisements; 3) Attitude toward the political party; and 4) Cognition about the political party. Responses about these 60 opinion statements were collected on five-point Likert scale (1= Strongly Disagreed; 2= Disagree; 3= Undecided; 4= Agree, 5= Strongly Agree). The survey was mainly conducted in-person from the respondents. Due to COVID-19, other options including online and email were also adopted to collect data in time. The researcher collected the data from January 2020 to June 2020.

5. Results and Analyses

5.1 Attitude toward Political Advertisements

Total 15 questions from 1000 respondents were asked in first scale to know the respondents' personal information, liking, disliking, and tendency of voting in previous general election, and inclination for voting in next election. The researcher asked the respondents to provide their opinion about advertisements of PPP, PML-N and PTI pertaining to easy to understand, create excitement, pleasant, informative and appropriate to project the manifesto of the party.

Table 5.1 PPP Political Advertisements Appropriate for Party Projection

			Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total
Gender of Participants	Male	Count	1	20	245	367	49	682
		% within Gender	0.1%	2.9%	35.9%	53.8%	7.2%	100.0%
	Female	Count	0	18	119	164	17	318
		% within Gender	0.0%	5.7%	37.4%	51.6%	5.3%	100.0%
Total		Count	1	38	364	531	66	1000
		% within Gender	0.1%	3.8%	36.4%	53.1%	6.6%	100.0%

According to the data given in above (table 5.1), there was high ratio of (53.8) males and (51.6) percent females agreed that political advertisements prepared and executed by the Pakistan People Party were appropriate for the projection of the party. Only (0.1) percent strongly disagreed and (2.9) percent males and (5.7) percent disagreed with the statement. However, (35.9) percent males and (37.4) percent females remained undecided in their opinion. So, majority of the participants agreed with the statement.

Table 5.2 PTI Political Advertisements are exciting

			Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Total
Gender of Participants	Male	Count	69	374	238	1	682
		% within Gender	10.1%	54.8%	34.9%	0.1%	100.0%
	Female	Count	26	177	113	2	318
		% within Gender	8.2%	55.7%	35.5%	0.6%	100.0%
Total		Count	95	551	351	3	1000
		% within Gender	9.5%	55.1%	35.1%	0.3%	100.0%

As per data given above (Table 5.2), the highest percentage of (54.8%) males and (55.7) percent females disagreed with the statement that advertisements made by the PTI are exciting, whereas (34.9) percent males and (35.5%) females remained undecided and only (0.3) percent males and females agreed with the statement. The analysis reveals that party projection by the PTI advertisements was insufficient and contrary to the wishes of the voters, who voted for the party in previous general election.

Table 5.3 PTI Political Advertisements are pleasant

			Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Total
Gender of Participants	Male	Count	50	366	260	6	682
		% within Gender	7.3%	53.7%	38.1%	0.9%	100.0%
	Female	Count	22	177	112	7	318
		% within Gender	6.9%	55.7%	35.2%	2.2%	100.0%
Total		Count	72	543	372	13	1000
		% within Gender	7.2%	54.3%	37.2%	1.3%	100.0%

As per gender-based analysis in above said (table 5.3), (7.3%) males and (6.9%) females strongly disagreed and (53.7%) males and (55.7%) females disagreed with the statement that advertisements made by the PTI are pleasant. A massive population comprising of (38.1%) males and (35.2%) females were found undecided in their opinion and only (1.3%) population agreed with the statement.

Table 5.4 PTI Political Advertisements are Informative

			Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Total
Gender of Participants	Male	Count	66	435	178	3	682
		% within Gender	9.7%	63.8%	26.1%	0.4%	100.0%
	Female	Count	24	196	95	3	318
		% within Gender	7.5%	61.6%	29.9%	0.9%	100.0%
Total		Count	90	631	273	6	1000
		% within Gender	9.0%	63.1%	27.3%	0.6%	100.0%

According to the above-said (Table, 5.3), only small population of (9.7%) males, (7.5%) females strongly disagreed, (63.8%) males and (61.1%) disagreed with the statement that political advertisements of PTI are informative. On the other side, (26.1) percent males and (27.3) percent females remained undecided. So, it can be argued that a huge population of (63.1) percent disagreed with the statement.

Table 5.5 PPP Political Advertisements are easy to understand

			Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total
Age of Participation	Below 19	Count	2	7	33	64	12	118
		% within Age	1.7%	5.9%	28.0%	54.2%	10.2%	100.0%
	Below 25	Count	1	7	82	215	78	383
		% within Age	0.3%	1.8%	21.4%	56.1%	20.4%	100.0%
	Below 30	Count	1	7	76	167	56	307
		% within Age	0.3%	2.3%	24.8%	54.4%	18.2%	100.0%
	Below 35	Count	0	8	38	91	24	161
		% within Age	0.0%	5.0%	23.6%	56.5%	14.9%	100.0%
	Above 36	Count	0	0	10	18	3	31
		% within Age	0.0%	0.0%	32.3%	58.1%	9.7%	100.0%
Total		Count	4	29	239	555	173	1000
		% within Age of Participation	0.4%	2.9%	23.9%	55.5%	17.3%	100.0%

As per age-wise analysis of given in the above (table 5.5), (10.2%) respondents below 19 years, (20.4%) below 25 years, (18.2%) below 30 years, (14.9%) below 35 years and (9.7%) respondents above 36 years of age strongly agreed with the statement that political advertisement made by PPP are easy to understand. Accordingly, (54.2%) respondents below 19 years, (56.1%) respondents below 25 years, (54.4%) below 30 years, (56.5%) below 35 and (58.1%) respondents above 36 years of age agreed with the above-said statement. Total (23.9%) respondents of all age remained undecided whereas (2.9%) disagreed and (0.4%) respondents of all age strongly disagreed with the statement.

Table 5.6 PMLN Political Advertisements are appropriate for party projection

			Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total
Age of Participation	Below 19	Count	6	46	32	26	8	118
		% within Age	5.1%	39.0%	27.1%	22.0%	6.8%	100.0%
	Below 25	Count	25	169	88	74	27	383
		% within Age	6.5%	44.1%	23.0%	19.3%	7.0%	100.0%
	Below 30	Count	16	149	68	59	15	307
		% within Age	5.2%	48.5%	22.1%	19.2%	4.9%	100.0%

	Below 35	Count	8	62	43	30	18	161
		% within Age	5.0%	38.5%	26.7%	18.6%	11.2%	100.0%
	Above 36	Count	3	12	7	7	2	31
		% within Age	9.7%	38.7%	22.6%	22.6%	6.5%	100.0%
Total		Count	58	438	238	196	70	1000
		% within Age	5.8%	43.8%	23.8%	19.6%	7.0%	100.0%

As per above (table 5.6), the data reveals, only (7) percent respondents of all age strongly agreed, (19.6%) agreed; (23.8%) respondents of all age remained undecided with the statement that the political advertisement were appropriate for party projection of the PMLN. Accordingly, the data further reveals that (43.8%) respondents of all age disagreed and (5.8%) strongly disagreed with the above-said statement that the political advertisements are appropriate for party projection of the PMLN.

Table 5.7 Intention in favor of the party (PMLN)

Variable	β	T	R	R^2	ΔR^2
Step 1			.061	0.009	0.002
Gender	-0.013	-0.404			
Age	0.011	0.335			
Education	0.053	1.665			
Step 2			.234	0.155	0.143
Gender	-0.011	-0.353			
Age	0.007	0.234			
Education	0.053	1.670			
Cognition towards ads of Party (PMLN)	0.185	3.341**			

Note. $N = 1000$; * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

H: Positive cognition about the advertisements of PTI will influence voter's intention in favor of this party. At first, relationship of two variables cognition about the advertisements of a particular political party (PTI) and voter's intention in favor of the party (PTI) was calculated with the help of Pearson correlation. The result shows that the both variables are positive and significantly related ($r=0.588$, $p<.05$, $N=1000$). After Pearson correlation, the hierarchical regression was performed to see the how much cognition about the advertisements of a particular political party (PTI) will influence voter's intention in favor of the party (PTI). At step 1 in hierarchical regression, the demographic variables (gender, age and education) were entered. The model was not fit and the demographic variable could not significantly contribute (accounted for .2% of the variation) towards dependent variables (voter's intention in favor of the party PTI). At step 2, the cognition about the advertisements of a particular political party (PTI) was entered which explained an additional 20.5% of variation in voter's intention in favor of the party PTI and the change in R^2 was statistically significant and model was fit, $F(4,995) = 80.86$, $p<.05$. The results of table 29 and 30 show that cognition about the advertisements of a particular political party (PTI) have a positive and significant influence on voter's intention in favor of the party (PTI). Thus, hypothesis H5c was supported.

Table 5.8 Pearson Correlation Table showing relationship between cognition about the advertisements of PTI and voter's intention in favor of the party (PTI).

		Cognition_ads_PT1	VIT_PT1
Cognition_ads_PT1	Pearson Correlation	--	
	N	1000	
VIT_PT1: Voters Intention towards_PT1	Pearson Correlation	.588**	--
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.001	
	N	1000	1098

Note. Correlation is significant at the * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$ (2-tailed).

Table 5.9 Summary of Hierarchical Regression Analysis for Variables predicting Voter's Intention in favor of the party (PTI)

Variable	β	t	R	R^2	ΔR^2
Step 1			.061	0.009	0.002
Gender	-0.013	-0.404			
Age	0.011	0.335			
Education	0.053	1.665			
Step 2			.466	0.217	0.207
Gender	-0.011	-0.353			
Age	0.010	0.319			
Education	0.054	1.700			
Cognition towards ads of Party (PTI)	0.442	9.020***			

Note. $N = 1000$; * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

H: Positive cognition about PPP will influence voter's intention in favor of this party.

At first, relationship of two variables cognition about a particular political party (PPP) and voter's intention in favor of the party (PPP) was calculated with the help of Pearson correlation. The result shows that the both variables are positive, weak and insignificantly related ($r=0.349$, $p>.05$, $N=1000$). After Pearson correlation, the hierarchical regression was performed to see the how much cognition about a particular political party (PPP) will influence voter's intention in favor of the party (PPP). At step 1 in hierarchical regression, the demographic variables (gender, age and education) were entered. The model was not fit and the demographic variable could not significantly contribute (accounted for .2% of the variation) towards dependent variables (voter's intention in favor of the party PPP). At step 2, the cognition about a particular political party (PPP) was entered which explained an additional .7% of variation in voter's intention in favor of the party PPP and the change in R^2 was not statistically significant and model was not fit, $F(4,995) = 1.56$, $p>.05$. The results of table 31 and 32 show that cognition about a particular political party (PPP) have a positive and insignificant influence on voter's intention in favor of the party (PPP). Thus, hypothesis H6a was not supported.

Table 5.10 Pearson Correlation Table showing relationship between cognition about PPP and voter's intention in favor of the party (PPP).

		Cognition about PPP	VIT_PPP
Cognition about PPP	Pearson Correlation	--	
	N	1000	
VIT_PPP: Voters Intention towards_PPP	Pearson Correlation	.349	--
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.302	
	N	1000	1098

Note. Correlation is significant at the * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$ (2-tailed).

Table 5. 11 Summary of Hierarchical Regression Analysis for Variables predicting Voter's Intention in favor of the party (PPP)

Variable	B	t	R	R ²	ΔR ²
Step 1			.061	0.009	0.002
Gender	-0.013	-0.404			
Age	0.011	0.335			
Education	0.053	1.665			
Step 2			.191	0.013	0.009
Gender	-0.013	-0.408			
Age	0.011	0.338			
Education	0.053	1.677			
Cognition about the Party (PPP)	0.137	0.907			

Note. N = 1000; *p < .05, **p < .01, ***p < .001

H: Positive cognition about PMLN will influence voter's intention in favor of this party. At first, relationship of two variables cognition about a particular political party (PMLN) and voter's intention in favor of the party (PMLN) was calculated with the help of Pearson correlation. The result shows that the both variables are positive and significantly related ($r=0.603$, $p<.05$, $N=1000$). After Pearson correlation, the hierarchical regression was performed to see the how much cognition about a particular political party (PMLN) will influence voter's intention in favor of the party (PMLN). At step 1 in hierarchical regression, the demographic variables (gender, age and education) were entered. The model was not fit and the demographic variable could not significantly contribute (accounted for .2% of the variation) towards dependent variables (voter's intention in favor of the party PMLN). At step 2, the cognition about a particular political party (PMLN) was entered which explained an additional 23.1% of variation in voter's intention in favor of the party PMLN and the change in R² was statistically significant and model was fit, $F(4,995) = 72.18$, $p<.05$. The results of table 33 and 34 show that cognition about a particular political party (PMLN) have a positive and significant influence on voter's intention in favor of the party (PMLN). Thus, hypothesis H6b was supported.

References

- Alina, M. O. (2020). Television engagement with followers on Facebook: a case study of nation television during the 2016 elections in Uganda. Centre for Communication Media and Society, Doctor of Philosophy, University of Kwazulu – Natal, CCMS Server.
- Anderson, L., & Stansfield, G. (2005). The future of Iraq: Dictatorship, democracy, or division? : Palgrave Macmillan.
- Bawn, K., Cohen, M., Karol, D., Masket, S., Noel, H., & Zaller, J. (2012). A theory of political parties: Groups, policy demands and nominations in American politics. *Perspectives on Politics*, 571-597.
- Beck, P. A., Dalton, R. J., Greene, S., & Huckfeldt, R. (2002). The social calculus of voting: Interpersonal, media, and organizational influences on presidential choices. *American Political Science Review*, 57-73.
- Belmonte, L. A. (2013). *Selling the American way: US propaganda and the Cold War*: University of Pennsylvania Press.
- Benoit, W. L. (2007). *Communication in political campaigns (Vol. 11)*: Peter Lang.
- Bilal, M., Malik, N., Bashir, N., Marjani, M., Hashem, I. A. T., & Gani, A. (2019). Profiling Social Media Campaigns and Political Influence: The Case of Pakistani Politics. Paper presented at the 2019 13th International Conference on Mathematics, Actuarial Science, Computer Science and Statistics (MACS).
- Blake, D. H. (2016). *Liking Ike: Eisenhower, advertising, and the rise of celebrity politics*: Oxford University Press.

9. Boltanski, L. (1999). *Distant suffering: Morality, media and politics*: Cambridge University Press.
10. Brown, A. R. (2013). Does money buy votes? the case of self-financed gubernatorial candidates, 1998–2008. *Political Behavior*, 35(1), 21-41.
11. Burki, S. J. (1988). Pakistan under Zia, 1977-1988. *Asian Survey*, 28(10), 1082-1100.
12. Centeno, M. A. (2002). *Blood and debt: War and the nation-state in Latin America*: Penn State Press.
13. Chapp, C. B. (2012). *Religious rhetoric and American politics: The endurance of civil religion in electoral campaigns*: Cornell University Press.
14. Cheibub, J. A., Gandhi, J., & Vreeland, J. R. (2010). Democracy and dictatorship revisited. *Public choice*, 143(1), 67-101.
15. Christians, C. G., Glasser, T., McQuail, D., Nordenstreng, K., & White, R. A. (2010). *Normative theories of the media: Journalism in democratic societies*: University of Illinois Press.
16. Cook, S. A. (2007). *Ruling but not governing: The military and political development in Egypt, Algeria, and Turkey*: JHU Press.
17. Dalton, R. J., Beck, P. A., & Huckfeldt, R. (1998). Partisan cues and the media: Information flows in the 1992 presidential election. *American Political Science Review*, 111-126.
18. Davis, M. (2007). *In praise of barbarians: Essays against empire*: Haymarket Books.
19. Dawson, J. I. (1996). *Eco-nationalism: Anti-nuclear activism and national identity in Russia, Lithuania, and Ukraine*: Duke University Press.
20. Deetz, S. (1992). *Democracy in an age of corporate colonization: Developments in communication and the politics of everyday life*: SUNY press.
21. Denton Jr, R. E., Trent, J. S., & Friedenber, R. V. (2019). *Political campaign communication: Principles and practices*: Rowman & Littlefield.
22. Derby, L. H. (2009). *The dictator's seduction: politics and the popular imagination in the era of Trujillo*: Duke University Press.
23. Dominick, J. R. (2010). *The dynamics of mass communication: Media in the digital age*: Tata McGraw-Hill Education.
24. Driscoll, A., & Nelson, M. J. (2014). Ignorance or opposition? Blank and spoiled votes in low-information, highly politicized environments. *Political Research Quarterly*, 67(3), 547-561.
25. Druckman, J. N. (2003). The power of television images: The first Kennedy-Nixon debate revisited. *The journal of politics*, 65(2), 559-571.
26. Dyer, R. (2004). *Heavenly bodies: Film stars and society*: Psychology Press.
27. Entman, R. M., & Rojecki, A. (2001). *The black image in the white mind: Media and race in America*: University of Chicago Press.
28. Esser, F. (2013). Mediatization as a challenge: Media logic versus political logic *Democracy in the Age of Globalization and Mediatization* (pp. 155-176): Springer.
29. Esser, F. (2013). Mediatization as a challenge: Media logic versus political logic *Democracy in the Age of Globalization and Mediatization* (pp. 155-176): Springer.
30. Farrell, D. M., Kolodny, R., & Medvic, S. (2001). Parties and campaign professionals in a digital age: Political consultants in the United States and their counterparts overseas. *Harvard International Journal of Press/Politics*, 6(4), 11-30.
31. Feagin, J. R., Vera, H., & Ducey, K. (2015). *Liberation sociology*: Routledge.
32. Finer, S. E. (2002). *The man on horseback: The role of the military in politics*: Transaction Publishers.
33. Frith, K. T., & Mueller, B. (2010). *Advertising and societies: Global issues*.
34. Fujiwara, T. (2015). Voting technology, political responsiveness, and infant health: Evidence from Brazil. *Econometrica*, 83(2), 423-464.
35. Gamson, W. A. (2004). Bystanders, public opinion, and the media. *The Blackwell companion to social movements*, 1, 242-264.
36. Gayer, L. (2014). *Karachi: Ordered disorder and the struggle for the city*: Oxford University Press (UK).
37. Geddes, B., Frantz, E., & Wright, J. G. (2014). Military rule. *Annual Review of Political*

- Science, 17, 147-162.
38. George, C. (2012). *Freedom from the press: Journalism and state power in Singapore*: NUS Press.
 39. Gershovich, M. (2000). *French military rule in Morocco: Colonialism and its consequences (Vol. 1)*: Psychology Press.
 40. Gibson, R. K. (2009). New media and the revitalisation of politics. *Representation*, 45(3), 289-299.
 41. Graham, T., & Hajru, A. (2011). Reality TV as a trigger of everyday political talk in the net-based public sphere. *European Journal of Communication*, 26(1), 18-32.
 42. Gregory, R., Failing, L., Harstone, M., Long, G., McDaniels, T., & Ohlson, D. (2012). *Structured decision making: a practical guide to environmental management choices*: John Wiley & Sons.
 43. Grigorovici, D. M., & Constantin, C. D. (2004). Experiencing interactive advertising beyond rich media: Impacts of ad type and presence on brand effectiveness in 3D gaming immersive virtual environments. *Journal of Interactive Advertising*, 5(1), 22-36.
 44. Hassan, K. (2018). Social Media, Media Freedom and Pakistan's War on Terror. *The Round Table*, 107(2), 189-202.
 45. Hendricks, J. A., & Schill, D. (2017). The social media election of 2016. *The 2016 US Presidential Campaign*, 121-150.
 46. Horten, G. (2003). *Radio goes to war: The cultural politics of propaganda during World War II*: Univ of California Press.
 47. Htoo, T. L. (2019). *Right to Information: Why is it important and what are the main challenges?*, University of Essex.
 48. Htun, M. (2004). Is gender like ethnicity? The political representation of identity groups. *Perspectives on Politics*, 439-458.
 49. Jacobs, L. R., & Shapiro, R. Y. (2000). *Politicians don't pander: Political manipulation and the loss of democratic responsiveness*: University of Chicago Press.
 50. Kapiszewski, A. (2006). Elections and parliamentary activity in the GCC States: Broadening political participation in the Gulf Monarchies. *Constitutional reform and political participation in the Gulf*, 4, 88.
 51. Katz, E., & Lazarsfeld, P. F. (1966). *Personal Influence, The part played by people in the flow of mass communications*: Transaction publishers.
 52. Kellner, D., & Share, J. (2007). Critical media literacy, democracy, and the reconstruction of education. *Media literacy: A reader*, 3-23.
 53. Kendall, K. E. (1995). *Presidential campaign discourse: strategic communication problems*: SUNY Press.
 54. Khan, A., & Naqvi, S. (2018). *Women in Politics: Gaining Ground for Progressive Outcomes in Pakistan*: IDS.
 55. Khan, A., Zhang, H., Shang, J., Boudjellal, N., Ahmad, A., Ali, A., & Dai, L. (2020). Predicting Politician's Supporters' Network on Twitter Using Social Network Analysis and Semantic Analysis. *Scientific Programming*, 2020.
 56. Kim, Y. (2017). Knowledge versus beliefs: How knowledge and beliefs mediate the influence of likeminded media use on political polarization and participation. *Journal of Broadcasting & Electronic Media*, 61(4), 658-681.
 57. Knoke, D. (1994). *Political networks: the structural perspective (Vol. 4)*: Cambridge University Press.
 58. Kunczik, M. (2003). Transnational public relations by foreign governments. *Handbook of global public relations*, 399-424.
 59. Kushner, B. (2007). *The thought war: Japanese imperial propaganda*: University of Hawaii Press.
 60. Legee, D. C., Wald, K. D., Krueger, B. S., & Mueller, P. D. (2009). *The politics of cultural differences: Social change and voter mobilization strategies in the post-new deal period*: Princeton University Press.
 61. Lenssen, G., Gasparski, W., Rok, B., Lacy, P., Albareda, L., Tencati, A., . . . Perrini, F.

- (2006). The government's role in promoting corporate responsibility: a comparative analysis of Italy and UK from the relational state perspective. *Corporate Governance: The international Journal of business in society*.
62. Lent, J. A. (1989). Mass communication in Asia and the Pacific: Recent trends and developments. *Media Asia*, 16(1), 16-24.
 63. MacDonald, D. B. (2003). *Balkan Holocausts?: Serbian and Croatian victim centred propaganda and the war in Yugoslavia*: Manchester University Press.
 64. Madon, S. (2000). *The Internet and socio- economic development: exploring the interaction*. Information technology & people.
 65. Masters, R. D., & Sullivan, D. G. (1990). Nonverbal behavior and leadership: Emotion and cognition in political information processing.
 66. Mazzoleni, G., & Schulz, W. (1999). "Mediatization" of politics: A challenge for democracy? *Political communication*, 16(3), 247-261.
 67. Michels, A., & De Graaf, L. (2010). Examining citizen participation: Local participatory policy making and democracy. *Local Government Studies*, 36(4), 477-491.
 68. Muslim, I., Kamboh, M. K., Saleem, A., & Jameel, M. (2014). Diffusion of Political Communication through Text Messages on Mobile Phones.
 69. Onis, Z. (1997). The political economy of Islamic resurgence in Turkey: The rise of the Welfare Party in perspective. *Third World Quarterly*, 18(4), 743-766.
 70. Parmelee, J. H., & Bichard, S. L. (2011). *Politics and the Twitter revolution: How tweets influence the relationship between political leaders and the public*: Lexington books.
 71. Prat, A., & Strömberg, D. (2005). *Commercial television and voter information*.
 72. Rao, M. F. (2020). Hate Speech and Media Information Literacy in the Digital Age: A Case Study of 2018 Elections in Pakistan. *Global Media Journal*, 18(34), 1-10.
 73. Rozumilowicz, B. (2002). Democratic change. *Media reform: Democratizing the media, democratizing the state*, 9(9).
 74. Shaw, D. R. (1999). The effect of TV ads and candidate appearances on statewide presidential votes, 1988-96. *American Political Science Review*, 345-361.
 75. Shirky, C. (2011). The political power of social media: Technology, the public sphere, and political change. *Foreign affairs*, 28-41.
 76. Smith, T. (2011). Brand salience not brand science: a brand narrative approach to sustaining brand longevity. *The Marketing Review*, 11(1), 25-40.
 77. Sohail, N. (2015). *Pakistan Ka Matlab Kya? (What does Pakistan Mean?) Decolonizing State and Society in 1960s and 1970s in Pakistan*. Tufts University.
 78. Sundström, A., Paxton, P., Wang, Y.-t., & Lindberg, S. I. (2017). Women's political empowerment: A new global index, 1900–2012. *World development*, 94, 321-335.
 79. Suwannathat-Pian, K. (2013). *Kings, country and constitutions: Thailand's political development 1932-2000*: Routledge.
 80. Tang, W. (2005). *Public opinion and political change in China*: Stanford University Press.
 81. Tybur, J. M., Merriman, L. A., Hooper, A. E. C., McDonald, M. M., & Navarrete, C. D. (2010). Extending the behavioral immune system to political psychology: Are political conservatism and disgust sensitivity really related? *Evolutionary Psychology*, 8(4), 147470491000800406.
 82. Vaccari, C., & Valeriani, A. (2015). Follow the leader! Direct and indirect flows of political communication during the 2013 Italian general election campaign. *New media & society*, 17(7), 1025-1042.
 83. Van Dijck, J. (2013). *The culture of connectivity: A critical history of social media*: Oxford University Press.
 84. Verplanken, B., & Holland, R. W. (2002). Motivated decision making: effects of activation and self-centrality of values on choices and behavior. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 82(3), 434.
 85. Vohs, K. D., Baumeister, R. F., Schmeichel, B. J., Twenge, J. M., Nelson, N. M., & Tice, D. M. (2014). Making choices impairs subsequent self-control: a limited-resource account of decision making, self-regulation, and active initiative.

-
86. Washbourne, N. (2010). *Mediating politics: newspapers, radio, television and the Internet*: McGraw-Hill Education (UK).
 87. Wilmshurst, L. (2013). *Clinical and Educational Child Psychology an Ecological-Transactional Approach to Understanding Child Problems and Interventions*: Wiley Online Library.
 88. Yezbick, R. S. (2009). *The costs of full citizenship: Navigating sites of contradiction in Arab Detroit post 9/11*: Michigan State University.
 89. Ziring, L. (1988). Public policy dilemmas and Pakistan's nationality problem: The legacy of Zia ul-Haq. *Asian Survey*, 28(8), 795-812.